

RESIDUAL STRESSES IN PARTICULATE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The residual stresses in a molten-metal-processed particulate reinforced metal matrix composite were measured by neutron diffraction. 2014 Al - 20 % SiC was studied in the as-cast, extruded and as-solution treated conditions. The magnitudes of the stresses are controlled by the relaxation mechanisms which occur during cooling from the processing temperature. Hot extrusion produces a net reduction in residual stress. Hot extrusion decreases the degree of particle clustering and increases particle alignment in the extrusion direction. This produces an anisotropy in the residual stress components with the axial stress component being much larger than the radial stress component. There is evidence of stress relaxation at room temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Residual stresses are an important feature of metal matrix composites (MMCs). The stress distribution in an MMC after processing is determined by a combination of factors which contribute to the magnitude of the stress (non-homogeneous elastic and plastic deformation, non-homogeneous thermal expansion/contraction), and relaxation mechanisms which lower the stress (diffusion, creep, dislocation punching). The particulate distribution controls both the stress enhancing factors and the relaxation mechanisms. Typically, the average residual stresses in particulate reinforced MMCs are tensile in the matrix and compressive in the particulate. The magnitude of the matrix stresses can be comparable to the yield stress, and could lead to dimensional instability due to creep or fracture initiation.

The residual stresses found in particulate reinforced MMCs following room temperature deformation have recently been examined by a number of investigators [1-3]. Their results indicated that the residual stresses produced by deformation quickly exceeds the thermal component of the residual stress [2], and achieve levels near the yield stress of the matrix. It is expected that more stress relaxation mechanisms should be activated at elevated temperatures. However, significant stress relaxation at room temperature has been reported for a deformed Al-matrix MMC [3]. The present study investigates the effects of hot extrusion on the residual stresses in a particulate reinforced MMC.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIAL

The material studied was molten-metal-processed 2014 Al -20 % SiC. This is a particulate - reinforced MMC produced by Alcan under the commercial name "Duralcan". Samples representing 3 stages of processing were supplied: i) as-cast (cylinder 54.0 mm diameter x 15.9 mm height), as-extruded 5:1 (25.4 mm diam. rod), and iii) as-extruded 20:1 (12.5 mm diam. rod). The extrusion temperature was 450°C. Samples of SiC particulate and unreinforced 2014 Al alloy were also supplied to provide stress-free reference standards for the diffraction measurements.

QUANTITATIVE METALLOGRAPHY

The particle spacing distributions were characterized by a tessellation method. An octagonal dilation routine was used to produce a tessellation of the particle distribution in each field, and frequency distributions of the tessellation cell area were computed from the resulting cell structures. The standard deviation of the cell area frequency distribution was used as the measure of particle clustering. The equivalent Poisson distribution was assumed to represent a random distribution [4].

INTERNAL STRESS MEASUREMENTS

Internal residual stresses in the Al 2014 matrix and the SiC particulate were determined by neutron diffraction measurements at ambient temperature made at the NRU reactor of AECL Research. Samples for the neutron diffraction experiments were prepared from the bulk MMC material and the Al 2014 alloy by electrical discharge machining to avoid any spurious residual stresses from the machining operation. The SiC powder was packed into a vanadium canister. The diffraction geometry is shown in Fig. 1. A single crystal Si monochromator provided a wavelength of 1.216Å. The (002)Al, (113)Al, (220)SiC and (440)SiC diffraction peaks were selected for strain measurements to avoid overlapping peaks. Gauss curves on sloping backgrounds were fitted to the data.

The internal strains were determined by comparing the measured lattice parameters in the MMC samples with the strain-free Al 2014 and SiC. If it is assumed that the stress state is pure hydrostatic, the internal residual stress is given by [5]

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = 3K \langle \epsilon \rangle = E \langle \epsilon \rangle / (1 - 2\nu) \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ = mean internal strain, $\langle \sigma \rangle$ = mean internal stress, and E, K, ν , are the isotropic elastic constants as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Isotropic Elastic Constants

Material	E GPa	K GPa	ν
Al 2014	73	71	0.33
SiC	469	236	0.17

measurements of strain as a function of tilt angle (ψ) [6]

$$\langle \epsilon_{\psi} \rangle = [(1+\nu)/E](\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle - \langle \sigma_{33} \rangle) \sin^2 \psi + (1/E)(\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle - 2\nu \langle \sigma_{11} \rangle) \quad (2)$$

Mean internal stresses were determined for each of the three MMC samples in the as-received condition. A second round of neutron diffraction measurements was carried out 18 months after the first experiments. Measurements were repeated on the as-cast and 20:1 extruded material. In addition, samples of as-cast, as- 20:1 extruded and unreinforced Al 2014 were heat treated 6 hr. at 510° C followed by water quenching, and the internal stresses determined for each.

RESULTS

QUANTITATIVE METALLOGRAPHY

Representative particle distributions are shown in Fig. 2. The mean values of particle diameter, aspect ratio and volume fraction are given in Table 2. Extrusion had little effect on either the mean diameter, aspect ratio, or the volume fraction of the particulate. There was no evidence of either particle cracking or debonding. In the as-cast condition (Fig. 2a), the particle distribution is markedly non-uniform. There are particle clusters and large particle-free areas (and some pores usually surrounded by particles). After extrusion, the particle distribution is much more uniform (Fig. 2b) and the porosity has been removed. The uniformity of the particulate distribution transverse to the extrusion axis is accompanied by an increased alignment of the particles in the extrusion direction (Fig. 2c).

Table 2. Summary of the Quantitative Metallographic Measurements on the Cast and Extruded Composites

Material	Particle Diameter (μm)	Particle Aspect Ratio	Volume Fraction
Cast	12.1 \pm 5	2.2 \pm 0.1	19.0
5:1	10.4 \pm 5	2.1 \pm 0.1	20.0
20:1	10.2 \pm 4	2.1 \pm 0.1	18.4

The tessellation cell area measurements confirm the qualitative observations on particle distributions. The frequency distributions of the tessellation cell areas are shown in Fig. 3, and compared to the equivalent Poisson distributions. The measured standard deviations (σ_{measured}) and the standard deviations of the equivalent Poisson distribution (σ_{Poisson}) are compared in Table 3. This shows that the particle distributions are clustered in all samples, and that the degree of clustering is reduced by the extrusion process.

Table 3. Summary of the Image Analysis Measurements.

Sample	Mean Cell Area (μm^2)	σ_{measured} (μm^2)	σ_{Poisson} (μm^2)	$\sigma_{\text{measured}}/\sigma_{\text{Poisson}}$
Cast	291	431	171	2.5
5:1 (Trans.)	230	286	152	1.9
20:1 (Trans.)	200	222	141	1.6
5:1 (Long.)	466	379	216	1.7
20:1 (Long.)	252	344	159	2.2

INTERNAL STRESS MEASUREMENTS

The complete data from the first round of experiments is shown in Fig. 4. The data from the extruded samples clearly indicates residual tensile strain in the Al 2014 matrix and compressive strain in the SiC particulate. In the as-cast material, the particulate has residual compressive strain, but the matrix has negligible strain. Table 4 gives the values of residual stress in each phase calculated for the hydrostatic case using eqn (1). (The $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ measurements for these calculations are the values taken at $\psi = 0$). Values of the hydrostatic $\langle \sigma \rangle$ obtained from the second round of experiments for the as-cast, as-extruded 20:1 sample and the two heat treated samples are also given in Table 4. To satisfy the equilibrium condition, the internal stresses must balance according to the equation

$$V_f \langle \sigma \rangle_{SiC} + (1 - V_f) \langle \sigma \rangle_{Al} = 0 \tag{3}$$

where V_f = vol. fraction of SiC. Calculated values of V_f (Table 3) show reasonable agreement with the measured values (Table 1), except for the as-cast material.

Table 4. Hydrostatic Stresses Calculated From Eqn (1).

Material	$\langle \sigma \rangle_{Al}$ MPa	$\langle \sigma \rangle_{SiC}$ MPa	V_f (calculated)
Cast (1st round)	-6 ± 37	-612 ± 42	-
Cast (2nd round)	-74 ± 14	-320 ± 58	-
5:1	144 ± 20	-575 ± 40	20
20:1 (1st round)	177 ± 28	-526 ± 17	25
20:1 (2nd round)	18 ± 11	-327 ± 41	5
Cast + heat treatment	73 ± 13	-538 ± 58	12
20:1 + heat treatment	111 ± 6	-549 ± 37	17

The variation in $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ with ψ (Fig. 4) indicates that the stress state is not pure hydrostatic for the extruded samples. The $\langle \epsilon_{33} \rangle$ component is much larger than the $\langle \epsilon_{11} \rangle$ component in all cases.

The normal stress components calculated from the variation in $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ with ψ using eqn (2) are given in Table 5. There are some anomalies in the results for the matrix stresses, especially for the as-cast samples. However, the stress components for the SiC particulate show consistent trends.

The highest values of stress occur in the as-cast or cast + heat treated conditions, and are nearly hydrostatic. With extrusion, the magnitudes of the stress components decrease and the $\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle / \langle \sigma_{11} \rangle$ ratio increases. The magnitudes of the stresses measured in the second round are less than in the first round for the same samples.

Table 5. Mean Stress Components as Calculated From Eqn (2).

Material	$\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_{Al}$ MPa	$\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_{Al}$ MPa	$\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_{SiC}$ MPa	$\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_{SiC}$ MPa
Cast (1st round)	0.004 ± 13	0.002 ± 13	-532 ± 24	-580 ± 8
Cast (2nd round)	-74 ± 54	-74 ± 46	-354 ± 32	-307 ± 47
5:1	124 ± 24	130 ± 28	-336 ± 18	-491 ± 6
20:1 (1st round)	130 ± 33	144 ± 28	-267 ± 18	-419 ± 6
20:1 (2nd round)	-14 ± 32	-3.4 ± 36	-245 ± 98	-312 ± 65
Cast + heat treatment	75 ± 70	73 ± 59	-566 ± 58	-521 ± 20
20:1 + heat treatment	40 ± 11	65 ± 10	-340 ± 54	-466 ± 54

DISCUSSION

The results from the first round measurements (Tables 4 and 5) show that hot-extrusion reduces the residual stresses from the values in the as-cast composite. This stress relaxation could occur during or immediately following hot-extrusion, by diffusion or by the generation and movement of dislocations. The second round measurements do not show a significant difference between the as-cast and as-extruded values. It appears that an overall reduction in the internal stresses occurred during the 18 months at room temperature between measurements. Since room temperature is approximately $0.3 T_m$, this could occur by diffusion or creep, as reported elsewhere [3]. However in all cases the stresses are increased by the heat treatment of 6 hr at 510°C followed by water quenching. The thermal component of the residual stress calculated by an Eshelby-type elastic model [7] for cooling Al 2014 - 20 % SiC from 510°C to room temperature is 288 MPa. Thus the thermal expansion effect is the source of all internal stresses. The stress values at room temperature in the as-cast and as-heat-treated samples are reduced from the maximum thermal value by relaxation involving diffusion during cooling of the former and dislocation punching during the quenching of the latter. Further reduction in stress occurs during hot-extrusion.

The ratio, $\langle\sigma_{33}\rangle/\langle\sigma_{11}\rangle$ increases with extrusion. This correlates with increasing alignment of the particulate in the extrusion direction (Table 3 and Fig. 2c). The alignment produces smaller mean particle spacing in the axial direction than in the radial direction. A reduction in the mean spacing constrains the matrix more effectively, inhibiting stress relaxation and results in larger residual stresses. The difference between $\langle\sigma_{33}\rangle$ and $\langle\sigma_{11}\rangle$ remained following heat treatment which confirms that it is an effect of the particle distribution.

The measured internal stresses for the 2014 Al matrix are inconsistent. The results for the as-cast samples seem to be influenced by the highly clustered particle distribution and large volume fraction of unconstrained particle free matrix and porosity. It is also difficult to determine the exact stress free lattice parameter of the matrix due to varying solute concentration.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Residual stresses in 2014 Al -20 % SiC are determined by the relaxation mechanisms which occur during cooling from the processing temperature.
2. Hot extrusion produces a net reduction in the residual stress.
3. Hot extrusion decreases the degree of particle clustering and increases particle alignment in the extrusion direction. This produces an anisotropy in the residual stress components with the axial stress component being much larger than the radial component.
4. There is evidence of stress relaxation at room temperature.

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Figure 1. Diffraction Geometry

Figure 2. Effect of Processing on the Distribution of the Particulate
 a) As-Cast b) 20:1 Extruded Transverse to the Extrusion Axis, and
 c) 20:1 Extruded Parallel to the Extrusion Axis

Figure 3. Cell Area Frequency Distributions and Standard Deviations
 a) As Cast b) 20:1 Extruded Transverse to the Extrusion Axis and
 c) 20:1 Extruded Parallel to the Extrusion Axis.

As Cast

5:1 Extrusion

20:1 Extrusion

Figure 4. Plots of $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ against $\sin^2 \psi$ for the As-Received Material